

CLASSICAL INSIGHTS ON VIDARIKAND (*PUERARIA TUBEROSA* DC.): A REVIEW OF
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ABSTRACT

Vidarikand (*Pueraria tuberosa* DC.), member of the family *Fabaceae*, a perennial, tuberous climber widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of India. The large starchy tubers are the principal medicinal part, valued for their sweet taste and cooling effect. It holds a significant place in traditional systems of medicine, especially *Ayurveda*, where it is regarded as a *Rasayana* drug known for its rejuvenating, nourishing, and strengthening properties. Traditionally, *Vidarikand* has been employed in the management of general debility, infertility, lactation insufficiency, respiratory ailments, and urinary disorders. Modern pharmacological studies further highlight its antioxidant, anti-diabetic, cardioprotective and immunomodulatory activities, thereby underscoring its significance in both classical and contemporary therapeutic applications. *Vidarikand* was reviewed in *Brihatrayee* and emerged out as a chief ingredient in various formulations especially indicated for *Vajikarana* and also found to be used as a *Bhawna dravya* or in the form of *Anupana*. Further, different *Ayurvedic* treatise in particular, *Bhaishjyarnavali*, *Yogratnakara* and others were observed for this purpose.

KEYWORDS: *Vidarikand*, *Pueraria tuberosa* DC., *Ayurvedic* treatise, *Samhita*, *Vajikarana*.

INTRODUCTION

Vidarikand (*Pueraria tuberosa* DC.) family *Fabaceae* as per API (Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India). *Vidarikand* is a perennial, woody climber, 10-30 m long with tuberous roots, up to 60 cm long and 30 cm thick, even weighing upto 35 kg, from about 5 or 10 kg in weight. It is found in dry and moist deciduous forest, including Sub-Himalayan tracts of the country, Eastern and Western Ghats and the Eastern and Southern Peninsular India.^[1]

Across *Ayurvedic* classical literatures, *Vidarikand* is consistently described as a rejuvenating and strength-promoting drug. The large starchy tubers are the principal medicinal part, valued for their sweet taste and cooling effect. Various *Ayurvedic samhitas* such as *Charaka samhita*, *Sushruta samhita* and *Nighantus* such as *Bhavaprakash Nighantu*, *Raja Nighantu*, *Dhanvantari Nighantu*, etc. have mentioned *Vidarikand* and its *Guna-Karma*, as *Madhura Rasa*, *Snigdha Guna*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Madhura Vipaka*. The *Vedas*—*Rigveda*, *Yajurveda*, *Samaveda*, and *Atharvaveda*, out of these canonical texts, *Rigveda* and *Atharvaveda* have abundant description and indications of plants but unfortunately no explicit reference regarding *Vidarikand*.^[2]

Charaka Samhita highlights *Vidarikand* as enhancing strength and lactation^[3], while *Sushruta Samhita* emphasizes its aphrodisiac and restorative properties.^[4] *Ashtanga Hridaya* recommends for balancing *Vata* and *Pitta* doshas and for urinary and respiratory disorders.^[5] *Nighantus* such as *Bhavaprakasha* and *Dhanvantari* further underscore its cooling, nutritive, and aphrodisiac effects.^{[6][7]} Across these texts, the plant is referred to by multiple synonyms—including *Vidari*, *Bhumikushmanda*, *Ikshugandha*, *Payasya* and many more reflecting diverse therapeutic applications and the continuity of its use from classical *Ayurveda* to contemporary medicine.^[8] A detailed review of *Vidarikand* was also done in a number of *Ayurvedic* treatise for multiple formulations in which *Vidarikand* has been included as an ingredient including but not limited to *Marmagutika*, *Satavaryadi Ghrita*, *Asvagandhadyarista*, *Nityananda Rasa*, *Sarasvatarista*, *Mahavisagarbha Taila*.^[9] *Rasa granthas*, *Kosha granthas* and various *Nighantus* were explored for its wide range of synonyms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Vidarikand in Samhita Kala****Charaka Samhita (1000B.C. - 4th Cent.A.D.)**

In Charak Samhita, the plant Vidarikand has been mentioned under *Madhur skandh* and *Kanthyia*, *Snehopaga Mahakashaya* (C.Su.4). It is also mentioned

as a *Shaka varga* (C.Su.27). Acharya Charak has thoroughly observed Vidarikand for its pharmacological properties and mentioned its therapeutic use in various diseases and widely used it in a variety of formulations.^[10]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Vatrakthar lepa</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>C.Su.3/21</i>
2.	<i>Chavanprash Rasayan</i>	<i>Kasa, Swas, Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Ci.1/1/62-69</i>
3.	<i>Pancham haritkyadi rasayan</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Ci.1/1/76</i>
4.	<i>Aamlak Ghrit</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Ci.1/2/4</i>
5.	<i>Indrokta rasayan</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Ci.1/4/6</i>
6.	<i>Indrokta rasayan param</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Ci.1/4/13-26</i>
7.	<i>Brahani gutika</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/1/24-32</i>
8.	<i>Vajikaran ghrit</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/1/33-37</i>
9.	<i>Apathyakari shastikadi gutika</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/2/3-9</i>
10.	<i>Vrishya ghrit</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/2/21</i>
11.	<i>Apatyakar kshir yoga</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/3/7-10</i>
12.	<i>Vrishya payas yoga</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/3/14</i>
13.	<i>Vrishya mashadi puplika</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/2/23-24</i>
14.	<i>Vrishya yoga</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/4/25-27</i>
15.	<i>Apatyakar ghrit</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/4/28-29</i>
16.	<i>Vrishya gutika</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>C.Ci.2/4/30-32</i>
17.	<i>Chandanadi tail</i>	<i>Daha, Jwar</i>	<i>C.Ci.3/258</i>
18.	<i>Shatavaryadi ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta</i>	<i>C.Ci.4/95-96</i>
19.	<i>Drakshadi ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaj gulma</i>	<i>C.Ci.5/123-125</i>
20.	<i>Jivantydi upnah swed</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>C.Ci.8/75-76</i>
21.	<i>Viradi pradeh</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>C.Ci.8/79</i>
22.	<i>Baladi nasaya</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>C.Ci.8/90</i>
23.	<i>Jivantyadi utsadan</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>C.Ci.8/175-177</i>
24.	<i>Kasadighrit</i>	<i>Apasmar</i>	<i>C.Ci.10/30</i>
25.	<i>Amritprash ghrit</i>	<i>Kshatkshin, Daha</i>	<i>C.Ci.11/35-43</i>
26.	<i>Tryushnadi ghrit</i>	<i>Kasa, Kshatkshin</i>	<i>C.Ci.18/37-49</i>
27.	<i>Yashtyadi vamak yoga</i>	<i>Pittaj kasa</i>	<i>C.Ci.18/84</i>
28.	<i>Vidaryadiyoga</i>	<i>Pittaj kasa</i>	<i>C.Ci.18/95</i>
29.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrit</i>	<i>Kshayaj kasa</i>	<i>C.Ci.18/151</i>
30.	<i>Vidaryadi ghritpak /dugdhpak</i>	<i>Mutravevarnya in Kasa</i>	<i>C.Ci.18/154</i>
31.	<i>Drahshadi churna</i>	<i>Pittaj chhardi</i>	<i>C.Ci.20/26</i>
32.	<i>Shatvaryadi lepa</i>	<i>Vataj-Pittaj Visarpa</i>	<i>C.Ci.21/24</i>
33.	<i>Darimadi lepa</i>	<i>Trishna</i>	<i>C.Ci.22/36</i>
34.	<i>Amrit ghrit</i>	<i>Visha</i>	<i>C.Ci.23/242-249</i>
35.	<i>Shatavaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Pittaj mutrakrichha</i>	<i>C.Ci.26/50</i>
36.	<i>Baladi tail</i>	<i>Shirorog</i>	<i>C.Ci.26/161-162</i>
37.	<i>Mahamayur ghrit</i>	<i>Shirorog</i>	<i>C.Ci.26/166-174</i>
38.	<i>Vidaryadi pan</i>	<i>Raktaj swarbheda</i>	<i>C.Ci.26/288</i>
39.	<i>Majjasneh</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	<i>C.Ci.28/124-127</i>
40.	<i>Amritadi tail</i>	<i>Vatavyadhi</i>	<i>C.Ci.28/157-164</i>
41.	<i>Parushakghrit</i>	<i>Vatashonit</i>	<i>C.Ci.29/58-60</i>
42.	<i>Jivkadi mahasneha</i>	<i>Vatashonit</i>	<i>C.Ci.29/72-75</i>
43.	<i>Sukumari tail</i>	<i>Vatashonit</i>	<i>C.Ci.29/96-102</i>
44.	<i>Takraarishtha</i>	<i>Pichil stanya chikitsa</i>	<i>C.Ci.30/278</i>
45.	<i>Ajagandhadi churna</i>	<i>Virechan yog</i>	<i>C.K.7/22</i>
46.	<i>Chandnadi niruha vasti</i>	<i>Daha, raktapitta, Pandu</i>	<i>C.K.3/48-52</i>
47.	<i>Drakshadi niruha vasti</i>	<i>Pitta nashak</i>	<i>C.K.3/53-55</i>
48.	<i>Saptprasatki vasti</i>	<i>Vrishya</i>	<i>C.Si.8/11</i>
49.	<i>Vidaryadi kawath</i>	<i>Shukra, Mamsa pushiti</i>	<i>C.Si.10/28</i>
50.	<i>Pratham Baladi yapna vasti</i>	<i>Madya klistanam saddho bala jannano</i>	<i>C.Si.12/15/5</i>

51.	<i>Chaturth Baladi yapna vasti</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>C.Si.12/15/10</i>
52.	<i>Mayuradi vasti</i>	<i>Bala varna vardhak</i>	<i>C.Si.12/17/3</i>
53.	<i>Chatur sneha anuvasana vasti</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Si.12/18/1</i>
54.	<i>Baladi anuvasan vasti</i>	<i>Virya, Bala, Mansa vrdhak</i>	<i>C.Si.12/18/2</i>
55.	<i>Sahachradi anuvasan vasti</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>C.Si.12/18/3</i>

Sushruta Samhita (1000 B.C. - 6th Cent.A.D)

In *Sushruta samhita*, *Vidarikand* has been described in *Vidarigandhadi gana*, *Valli panchamoola*, *Pitta sanshaman* and *Madhura varga*. *Acharya Sushrut*

mentioned *Vidarikand* in *Kanda varga*. He listed various therapeutic uses of *Vidarikand* and included it as an ingredient in several formulations.^[11]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Sitadi choorna</i>	<i>Daha, Jwar</i>	<i>S.Su.47/17</i>
2.	<i>Ashwakarnadi churna</i>	<i>Saddhovrana</i>	<i>S.Ci. 2/64-65</i>
3.	<i>Sahadi pradeha</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>S.Ci.5/12</i>
4.	<i>Kushadi ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaj ashmari</i>	<i>S.Ci.7/9-13</i>
5.	<i>Vidaryadi nashya</i>	<i>Krimidant</i>	<i>S.Ci.22/40</i>
6.	<i>Tiladi utkarika</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>S.Ci.26/23</i>
7.	<i>Vidarikand yoga</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>S.Ci.26/23</i>
8.	<i>Vidrimoola yoga</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>S.Ci.26/28</i>
9.	<i>Mashadi kshir</i>	<i>Vajikar</i>	<i>S.Ci.26/36</i>
10.	<i>Bhutikadi tail</i>	<i>Vatvyadhi (vasti)</i>	<i>S.Ci.37/19-22</i>
11.	<i>Kushadi asthapan vasti</i>	<i>Vasti</i>	<i>S.Ci.38/51-54</i>
12.	<i>Vidarigana siddha tail</i>	<i>Mand vish/ Vrishchika dansh</i>	<i>S.K.8/70</i>
13.	<i>Vidaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Luta vish</i>	<i>S.K.8/132</i>
14.	<i>Aswgandhadi kwath</i>	<i>Revwti grah</i>	<i>S.U.31/3</i>
15.	<i>Vidaryadi lepa</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>S.U.39/303</i>
16.	<i>Vidaryadi choorna</i>	<i>Pittaj shool</i>	<i>S.K.42/71</i>

Ashtang Hridayam (7th Century A.D.)

Acharya Vagbhatta mentioned *Vidarikand* in *Shaka varga*, *Madhur gana* and *Vidaryadi gana*. *Vidarikand* has

been indicated in several diseases for its therapeutic uses and also in various formulations.^[12]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Kapitthadi lepa</i>	<i>Daha, Vedna, Moha</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.1/134-135</i>
2.	<i>Vidari rasa</i>	<i>Pittaj kasa</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/26</i>
3.	<i>Medadi ghrit</i>	<i>Pittaj kasa</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/38-40</i>
4.	<i>Amritprash ghrit</i>	<i>Kasa, Nastshukra, Kshatkshin</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/94-101</i>
5.	<i>Dhatri ghrit</i>	<i>Kasa, Mamsa shukra vardhak</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/108-109</i>
6.	<i>Vidari swaras siddh ghrit</i>	<i>Kshayaj Kasa</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/153</i>
7.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrit payam</i>	<i>Kshayaj kasa</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.3/155</i>
8.	<i>Baladi ghrita</i>	<i>Swarbhed</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.5/41</i>
9.	<i>Punarnvadi lepa</i>	<i>Rajyakshama pinas</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.5/68</i>
10.	<i>Jivantyadi urdhvartan</i>	<i>Rajyakshama pushtivardhak</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.5/78-80</i>
11.	<i>Vidaryadi ambu</i>	<i>Vataj trishna</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.6/68</i>
12.	<i>Shatavaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Mutrghat</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.11/6</i>
13.	<i>Kushadi ghrit</i>	<i>Pittaj Ashmari</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.11/22-24</i>
14.	<i>Vidari varg siddha traivat sneha</i>	<i>Vrana ropana</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.13/3</i>
15.	<i>Drakshadi ghrit</i>	<i>Vidradhi, Moha, Mada nashak</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.13/16-17</i>
16.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrit</i>	<i>Vatodara</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.15/53</i>
17.	<i>Vidaryadi kshir</i>	<i>Pittodar</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.15/64</i>
18.	<i>Aragvadadi pana</i>	<i>Kamla</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.16/41</i>
19.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrita</i>	<i>Aptanak</i>	<i>A.H.Ci.21/27</i>
20.	<i>Ajagandhadi yoga</i>	<i>Virechan yoga, Jwar</i>	<i>A.H.K.2/10-11</i>
21.	<i>Rasnadi kalpa</i>	<i>Atisar, Kamla, Raktapitta</i>	<i>A.H.K.4/12-16</i>
22.	<i>Paysyadi kwath</i>	<i>Shukrakarak vasti</i>	<i>A.H.K.4/25</i>
23.	<i>Mayur vasti</i>	<i>Bala and Shukrakarak</i>	<i>A.H.K.4/45-46</i>
24.	<i>Kasadi dugdha</i>	<i>Apasmar</i>	<i>A.H.U.7/28</i>

25.	<i>Utpaladi paya</i>	<i>Kshataj Shukra</i>	<i>A.H.U.11/31</i>
26.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrit</i>	<i>Vataj pratishyay</i>	<i>A.H.U.20/10</i>
27.	<i>Vidaryadi tail</i>	<i>Dantashul</i>	<i>A.H.U.22/25</i>
28.	<i>Mahamayur ghrit</i>	<i>Shiroroga, Indriyabhransh, Shukradosh</i>	<i>A.H.U.24/49-55</i>
29.	<i>Chyavanprash</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>A.H.U.39/33-41</i>
30.	<i>Sharadi yoga</i>	<i>Vajikara</i>	<i>A.H.U.40/12-20</i>
31.	<i>Vidaryadhavleha</i>	<i>Vajikara</i>	<i>A.H.U.40/21-22</i>
32.	<i>Vidarikand churnakriya</i>	<i>Vajikara</i>	<i>A.H.U.40/26</i>

Ashtang Sangraha (7th century A.D.)

In *Ashtang Samgraha*, *Vidarikand* is mentioned in *Balya Mahakshaya*. *Vidarikand* has been mentioned in the text of *Ashtang Samgraha* under numerous formulations.^[13]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Vidari guna</i>	<i>Annaroopvigyaneeeya adhyaya</i>	<i>A.S.Su.-7/120</i>
2.	<i>Kashmaryadi ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-4/5</i>
3.	<i>Vidaryadi ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-4/7</i>
4.	<i>Vidaryadi paana</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-4/18</i>
5.	<i>Medadi sarpi</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-4/27</i>
6.	<i>Baladi sarpigud</i>	<i>Kshatkshayaj Kasa</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-5/26</i>
7.	<i>Sansrishtadosha pradeha</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.7/42</i>
8.	<i>Jeevanyadi churna udvartan</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>A.S.Ci.-7/52</i>
9.	<i>Putrada rasayana basti</i>	<i>Siddha basti kalpa</i>	<i>A.S.Ka.-5/15</i>
10.	<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Kshudra rog</i>	<i>A.S.U.-36/19</i>
11.	<i>Shirishtwagadi ghrita</i>	<i>Visha pratisheda</i>	<i>A.S.U.-40/75</i>
12.	<i>Chawanprash</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>A.S.U.-49/25</i>
13.	<i>Swaguptadi churna</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>A.S.U.-50/17</i>
14.	<i>Jeevakadi ghrita</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>A.S.U.-50/51</i>
15.	<i>Grshyadi ksheer (dwitya prayog)</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>A.S.U.-50/54</i>
16.	<i>Vrshyabhakshya peya</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>A.S.U.-50/61</i>

Kashyapa Samhita (600-1000 B.C.)

The *Kashyapa Samhita* (also known *Vrdha Jivakiya Tantra*) as composed by a renowned ancient scholar,

Vridha Jivaka has mentioned *Vidarikand* and its formulations for treating disorders of children.^[14]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
2.	<i>Bala taila</i>	<i>Dhatri chikitsa</i>	<i>K.S.Ci</i>

Harita Samhita (600-1000 B.C.)

Vidarikand has also been mentioned by *Acharya Harita* in different formulations for various diseases as

exemplified by *Vidaryadi lepa*, *Mridwikadi dugdh paka*, *Vidarikadi churna*.^[15]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Vidaryadi Lepa</i>	<i>Trishna, Murchha</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 2/73</i>
2.	<i>Drakshadi kwath</i>	<i>Trivagni samam, Pushthikar</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 6/19</i>
3.	<i>Shatavariyadi dugdh</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 10/51</i>
4.	<i>Mridwikadi dugdh paka</i>	<i>Stri rog</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 10/52</i>
5.	<i>Vidarikadi churna</i>	<i>Klevya</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 47/8</i>
6.	<i>Vidarkandadi churna</i>	<i>Klevya</i>	<i>Ha.S.Tri 47/16</i>

Sharandhar Samhita (13th Century A.D.)

Vidarikand has been mentioned in *Purva khand* of *Sharandhar Samhita* in various formulations as an ingredient.^[16]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	Mashadi churna	Vajikarana	S.S.M.6
2.	Chawanprash avleha	Rasayana	S.S.M.8
3.	Kamdev ghrita	Vajikarana	S.S.M.9
4.	Kandarpasundar ras	Grahani	S.S.M.12

Bhela Samhita

Few formulations have been listed in *Bhela samhita* including *Vidarikand* as an ingredient for instance *Rasayani sarpi* (B.S.Ci.4/34-40), *Sarpigud* (B.S.Ci.4/34-40), *Sarpi modak* (B.S.Ci.4/34-40), *Tilsarpi modak* (B.S.Ci.4/41-53), *Mahanimbadi taila* (B.S.Ci.16/70-73) and *Kakadanyadi ghrita* (B.S.Ci.26/20-23).^[17]

Bhavprakasha Samhita (16th Century A.D.)

Bhavprakash samhita documented *Vidarikand* in *Jeevakaj mishrak*, *Vidarkandadi churna*, *Sudarshan churna*, *Strirativallabh poogpaka* and others.^[18]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Sudarshan churna</i> (Use of <i>Vidarikand</i> in <i>abhava</i> of <i>Jeevak</i> and <i>Rshbhak</i>)	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-1/125-135</i>
2.	<i>Vidarikandadi churna</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-29/34</i>
3.	<i>Vidarikandadi kwath</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-29/39</i>
4.	<i>Jeevakaaj mishrak</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-29/152</i>
5.	<i>Vidarikand ras</i> (for <i>basti</i>)	<i>Pittaj Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-35/16</i>
6.	<i>Shatavaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Pittaj Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-35/18</i>
7.	<i>Shatavari ghrita ksheer</i>	<i>Pittaj Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-35/21</i>
8.	<i>Vallipanchmool</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-35/46</i>
9.	<i>Sukumar kumarak punarnavadya avaleha</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-35/50</i>
10.	<i>Bhadravaha ghrita</i>	<i>Mutraghaat</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-36/42</i>
11.	<i>Vidari ghrita</i>	<i>Mutraghaat</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-36/47</i>
12.	<i>Kushadi ghrita</i>	<i>Pittak Ashmari</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-37/23</i>
13.	<i>Vidarikandadi churna</i>	<i>Som rog</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-69/8</i>
14.	<i>Vidarikandadi kalka with dugdha</i>	<i>Garbhini pratimaas chikitsa</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-70/95-96</i>
15.	<i>Vidarikandadi kwath</i> (for <i>sechan</i>)	<i>Baal rog</i> (<i>Revti grahjusht chikitsa</i>)	<i>Bh. Ci.-71/75</i>
16.	<i>Navpayasyadya kalka taila</i> (for <i>abhyanga</i>)	<i>Baal rog</i> (<i>Putna grahjusht chikitsa</i>)	<i>Bh. Ci.-71/84</i>
17.	<i>Strirativallabh poogpaka</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Bh. Ci.-72/33-38</i>

Bhaishajyaratnavali (18th Century A.D.)

Govindadas Sen's renowned *Ayurvedic* treatise, "*Bhaishajyaratnavali*" recognized for its specialization

in the field of medicine, encompasses a wide array of therapeutic formulations.^[19]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Maharaj vati</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>B.R.5/1120</i>
2.	<i>Lakshmi vilaas ras</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>B.R.5/1224</i>
3.	<i>Shrikameshwar modak</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	<i>B.R. 8/157</i>
4.	<i>Chandrasuryatmak ras</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	<i>B.R.12/76</i>
5.	<i>Kamdev ghrita</i>	<i>Rakpitta</i>	<i>B.R. 13/145</i>
6.	<i>Parashar ghrita</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>B.R.14/241-242</i>
7.	<i>Nityodaya ras</i>	<i>Kaas</i>	<i>B.R.15/148</i>
8.	<i>Vrshdhvaj ras</i>	<i>Chardi</i>	<i>B.R.19/25</i>
9.	<i>Eladya modak</i>	<i>Madatya</i>	<i>B.R.22/22-24</i>
10.	<i>Mahachaitas ghrita</i>	<i>Apasmaar</i>	<i>B.R.25/44</i>
11.	<i>Gaganadi vati</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>B.R.26/129</i>
12.	<i>Maashbaladi taila</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>B.R.26/587</i>
13.	<i>Mahavishgarbha taila</i> (<i>mahat</i>)	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>B.R.26/598</i>
14.	<i>Guduchi taila</i> (<i>brihat</i>)	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>B.R.27/141</i>
15.	<i>Poogkhandopar</i>	<i>Shool</i>	<i>B.R.30/221</i>
16.	<i>Drakshadya ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	<i>B.R.32/149</i>
17.	<i>Bhallatak ghrita</i> (<i>pratham</i>)	<i>Gulma</i>	<i>B.R.32/159</i>

18.	<i>Vidaryadi kwath</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>B.R.34/18</i>
19.	<i>Sukumarak ghrita</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>B.R.34/60</i>
20.	<i>Bhadravaham ghrita</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>B.R.35/38</i>
21.	<i>Kushadyam ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaj ashmari</i>	<i>B.R.36/59</i>
22.	<i>Daadimadya ghrita</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>B.R.37/219</i>
23.	<i>Vrihachyamadi ghrita</i>	<i>Prameha pidika</i>	<i>B.R.38/16,18</i>
24.	<i>Trivritadi ghrita</i>	<i>Vridhhi rog</i>	<i>B.R.43/96</i>
25.	<i>Danti ghrita</i>	<i>Vridhhi rog</i>	<i>B.R.43/102</i>
26.	<i>Sarivadyavleha</i>	<i>Updansh rog</i>	<i>B.R.52/68</i>
27.	<i>Anantadhya ghrita</i>	<i>Updansh rog</i>	<i>B.R.52/74</i>
28.	<i>Vidaryadi taila</i>	<i>Mukhrog</i>	<i>B.R.61/133</i>
29.	<i>Madhukadhyavleha</i>	<i>Pradar</i>	<i>B.R.66/37</i>
30.	<i>Kumar kalpadrum ghrita</i>	<i>Yonivyapad</i>	<i>B.R.67/97</i>
31.	<i>Garbhavilaas taila</i>	<i>Garbhini rog</i>	<i>B.R.68/99</i>
32.	<i>Saubhagya sunthi (brihat)</i>	<i>Sutika rog</i>	<i>B.R.69/39</i>
33.	<i>Stanya vardhan upaya</i>	<i>Stanrog</i>	<i>B.R.70/1</i>
34.	<i>Shiva modak</i>	<i>Baalrog</i>	<i>B.R.71/106</i>
35.	<i>Saraswatarishta</i>	<i>Rasayan</i>	<i>B.R.73/183</i>
36.	<i>Vajikarmanya pathya yog</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/26,29</i>
37.	<i>Narsingh churna</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/40</i>
38.	<i>Manmathabhra ras</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/98</i>
39.	<i>Kameshvar modak (dwitya)</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/186</i>
40.	<i>Kaamagnisandeepan modak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/202</i>
41.	<i>Mahakameshwar modak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/232</i>
42.	<i>Shrimadananand modak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>B.R.74/245</i>
43.	<i>Arjakadi vati</i>	<i>Veeryasatmbh</i>	<i>B.R.75/13</i>
44.	<i>Yamanyadi churna</i>	<i>Gadodvega</i>	<i>B.R.78/7</i>
45.	<i>Shatavari ghrita</i>	<i>Snayurog</i>	<i>B.R.82/18</i>
46.	<i>Somrog nashak yog</i>	<i>Bahumutra</i>	<i>B.R.86/10</i>
47.	<i>Makshikadi churna</i>	<i>Shukrameha</i>	<i>B.R.88/26</i>
48.	<i>Kandarpasundar ras</i>	<i>Dhwajbhanga</i>	<i>B.R.92/42</i>

Yogratnakar (17th Century A.D.)

Yogratnakar divided into two parts i.e. *Purvardha* and *Uttarardha*. Here, *Vidarikand* has been described in the

Abhava varga. In this treatise, *Vidarikand* has been described in ample amount of formulations as an ingredient for the treatment of various disorders.^[20]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Muktapanchamrit ras</i>	<i>Jwar</i>	<i>Jwar</i>
2.	<i>Shadshiti guggul</i>	<i>Vaat vyadhi</i>	<i>Vaat vyadhi</i>
3.	<i>Dhatrayadi yog</i>	<i>Shool</i>	<i>Shool</i>
4.	<i>Drakshadi ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaj Gulma</i>	<i>Gulma</i>
5.	<i>Shatavaryadi sarpi</i>	<i>Pittaj Mutrakriccha</i>	<i>Mutrakriccha</i>
6.	<i>Jalajamrit ras</i>	<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Prameha</i>
7.	<i>Sheetkalyanak ghrita</i>	<i>Somrog</i>	<i>Somrog</i>
8.	<i>Vidarikand churna</i>	<i>Somrog</i>	<i>Somrog</i>
9.	<i>Vidarikandadi ksheerpak</i>	<i>Strirog</i>	<i>Strirog</i>
10.	<i>Vidarikand churna with sura</i>	<i>Prasuta stanyajanan</i>	<i>Balrog</i>
11.	<i>Vidarikandadi churna</i>	<i>Karshya</i>	<i>Balrog</i>
12.	<i>Vidarikandadi Kwath</i>	<i>Balgrha</i>	<i>Balrog</i>
13.	<i>Shatavaryadi churna</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>
14.	<i>Vidarikand churna</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>
15.	<i>Amrit bhallatak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>
16.	<i>Rativallabh poog paak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>
17.	<i>Kamagnisandeepan modak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>
18.	<i>Durvadi ghrita</i>	<i>Ras vaikriti</i>	<i>Ras vaikriti</i>

Siddhasara Samhita (7th century A.D.)

Vidarikand used in various disorders as an ingredient in many formulations namely *Kshayahar leha*,

Shatavaryadi rasayan, *Chaar panchmool*, *Laghu Chawanprash* and *Raktapitta nashak ghrita*.^[21]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Raktapitta nashak ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta</i>	<i>Si.S.7/25-26</i>
2.	<i>Kshayahar leha</i>	<i>Kshaya rog (Yakshma)</i>	<i>Si.S.8/15</i>
3.	<i>Laghu Chawanprash</i>	<i>Kshaya rog</i>	<i>Si.S.8/26-31</i>
4.	<i>Chaar panchmool</i>	<i>Visarpa</i>	<i>Si.S.23/8</i>
5.	<i>Shatavaryadi rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana/Vajikaran</i>	<i>Si.S.28/15</i>
6.	<i>Vidarikand yog</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Si.S.28/20</i>

Vidarikand in other valuable Ayurvedic treatise Vaidyaprasarakam (9th century A.D.)

The author of above book is *Vaidya Acharya Gadadhara*, mentioned *Vidarikand* as an ingredient of

various formulations *Amritadhyam*, *Mahamayura* and *Ashwagandhadhyam*.^[22]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Narsimha churna</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>V.Pr. 2- Pg-129</i>
3.	<i>Amritadhyam</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>V.Pr. 4- Pg-284</i>
4.	<i>Mahamayuram</i>	<i>Shukra dosha/ Bandhyatva</i>	<i>V.Pr. 5- Pg-370</i>
5.	<i>Ashwagandhadhyam</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	<i>V.Pr. 5- Pg- 353</i>
6.	<i>Chawanprash</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>V.Pr. 6- Pg-381</i>
7.	<i>Virechana yog</i>	<i>Virechan</i>	<i>V.Pr.10- Pg-518</i>
8.	<i>Sarpiguda</i>	<i>Urahkshata</i>	<i>V.Pr.10- Pg-558</i>
9.	<i>Sarpiguda II</i>	<i>Kshayarog</i>	<i>V.Pr.10- Pg-561</i>

Chikitsakalika (10th century A.D.)

The Author *Tista Acharya*, (son of *Vagbhata*) of “*Chikitsakalika*” an important treatise described many

formulations with *Vidarikand* as an ingredient for instance, *Phal ghrita* and *Shukradhatu vriddhikar yog*.^[23]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Raktapitta nashak ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta</i>	<i>Chi. Ka. Raktapitta-shlok 239-240</i>
2.	<i>Chawanprash rasayana</i>	<i>Kshaya rog</i>	<i>Chi. Ka. Kshaya-shlok 266</i>
3.	<i>Amritprash</i>	<i>Kshaya</i>	<i>Chi. Ka. Kshaya-shlok 270</i>
4.	<i>Phalghrita</i>	<i>Bandhyatva</i>	<i>Chi. Ka. Bhootvidya-shlok 376</i>
5.	<i>Shukradhatu vriddhikar yog</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Chi. Ka. Vajikaran-shlok 402</i>

Vangsen Samhita (12th century A.D.)

The *Vangsen Samhita* also famous as *Chikitsasara-Sangraha* containing 104 chapters mentioned *Vidarikand* in various formulations.^[24]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Brihat shatavari ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta</i>	<i>V.S.-Raktapitta/117</i>
2.	<i>Kaamdev ghrita</i>	<i>Raktapitta</i>	<i>V.S.-Raktapitta/130</i>
3.	<i>Chawanprash avaleha</i>	<i>Rajyakshma</i>	<i>V.S.-Rajyakshma/143</i>
4.	<i>Sarpiguda</i>	<i>Kshatkshaya</i>	<i>V.S.- Kshatkshaya/44</i>
5.	<i>Ashwagandhadhya ghrita</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	<i>V.S.-Kasa/103</i>
6.	<i>Mahachaitas ghrita</i>	<i>Apasmaar</i>	<i>V.S.-Apasmaar/61</i>
7.	<i>Mahaashalvan sweda</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatvyadhi/67</i>
8.	<i>Mahakalyanak taila</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatvyadhi/277</i>
9.	<i>Samishmahamaash taila</i>	<i>Vaatvyadhi</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatvyadhi/338</i>
10.	<i>Vaatrakta nashak lepa</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatrakta/37</i>
11.	<i>Kaishore guggul</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatrakta/161</i>
12.	<i>Shiv gutika</i>	<i>Vaatrakta</i>	<i>V.S.-Vaatrakta/194</i>
13.	<i>Shalparni taila</i>	<i>Udar rog</i>	<i>V.S.-Udar rog/113</i>
14.	<i>Jeevakadya taila</i>	<i>Shiro rog</i>	<i>V.S.-Shiro rog/119</i>
15.	<i>Godhumadhya ghrita</i>	<i>Vajikarana</i>	<i>V.S.-Vajikarana/81</i>

Vaidyarahasya (13th century A.D.)

Notably, *Vidarikand* is mentioned as an ingredient in several preparations for the treatment of various ailments in this treatise.^[25]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Ashwagandhadi vati</i>	<i>Pradar roga</i>	<i>Vd. Rh. Streerog chikitsa-shlok 21</i>
2.	<i>Mashadi yog</i>	<i>Somroga</i>	<i>Vd. Rh. Streerog chikitsa-shlok 36</i>
3.	<i>Kamdev churna</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vd. Rh. Vajikaranadhikar-shlok 7</i>
4.	<i>Supari pak</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Vd. Rh. Vajikaranadhikar-shlok 25</i>

Abhinav-navajivanam

This significant text, comprising 16 chapters, presents a wide range of formulations intended for the treatment of

various diseases. Among these, *Vidarikand*, featured as an ingredient in multiple preparations.^[26]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Drakshadyam ghrita</i>	<i>Pittaj Kasa</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 2/78</i>
2.	<i>Mahatrayushna ghrita</i>	<i>Vata roga</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 2/162</i>
3.	<i>Sharmooliyam ghrita</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 2/224-228</i>
4.	<i>Samdugdhakam ghrita</i>	<i>Vajikaran</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 2/239</i>
5.	<i>Mahamasha taila</i>	<i>Vata roga</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 2/128</i>
6.	<i>Chawanprash avaleha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 4/25</i>
7.	<i>Pittahar basti</i>	<i>Pittaj Vikar</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 5/32</i>
8.	<i>Ashwagandha Rasayana</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 6/1</i>
9.	<i>Vidari churna</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 8/27</i>
10.	<i>Vidaryadi prayog</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 8/28</i>
11.	<i>Vidaryadi Puplica</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 8/30</i>
12.	<i>Vidari yog</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 8/32</i>
13.	<i>Saraswat ghrita</i>	<i>Vrshya</i>	<i>Abhi. Na. 8/37</i>

**Vidarikand in Ras-Grantha
Rasaratnasamuccaya**

The text encompasses numerous formulations involving metallic and herbal components. Notably, *Vidarikand*

has been mentioned as an ingredient in several formulations.^[27]

S.NO.	PREPARATION	INDICATIONS	REF. NO.
1.	<i>Chandravaleha</i>	<i>Pittaj roga</i>	<i>Ras. Rat. Sa. 21/274</i>
2.	<i>Amritprash churna</i>	<i>Pittaj vikar</i>	<i>Ras. Rat. Sa. 21/177</i>

**Vidarikand in Kosha-Grantha
Amar Kosha (5th Century A.D.)**

Vidarikand is mentioned in *Dwitya Kand* in *Vanaushadhi Varga* in verse 110 in *Amar Kosha*. Here four synonyms of *Vidarikand* are mentioned as *Vidari*, *Ksheershukla*, *Ikshugandha*, *Koshtri*.^[28]

Bhumikushmanda, *Shukla*, *Ikshuganda*, *Koshtri*, *Vidarika*, *Swadukanda*, *Sita*, *Shringalika*, *Vrshyakanda*, *Vidaali*, *Vrshyavallika*, *Bhukushmandi*, *Swadulata*, *Gajeshtha* and *Vaarivallabha*.^[29]

Shabdakalpadruma (20th Century A.D.)

The *Shabdakalpadruma Kosha* was written by Raja Radhakant Dev in 20th century. The *Kosha* describes various synonyms of *Vidarikand* such as

Bedi-Vanaspati-Kosha

The author Prof. Ramesh well described *Vidarikand* featured as *Vidalika*, *Vidali*, *Vidarika*, *Vidari*, *Vidarikand*, *Bilaikand*, *Bhuikohada* and *Bhumikushmanda*.^[30]

Classification of Vidarikand in different Nighantu at a glance

S. No.	Nighantu	Gana/Varga	Reference
1.	<i>Saushrut Nighantu</i>	<i>Vidarigandhadi gana</i>	<i>Sau. Ni. Vidarigandhadi gana (Pg. 3)</i>
2.	<i>Astanga Nighantu</i>	<i>Vidaryadi gana</i>	<i>As. Ni. Vidaryadi gana (Pg. 2)</i>
3.	<i>Paryayaratnamala</i>	-	<i>Pray. (Pg. 24)</i>
4.	<i>Madanadi Nighantu</i>	<i>Vidaryadi gana</i>	<i>Madn. Ni. Vidaryadi gana (Pg. 87)</i>
5.	<i>Dhanvantari Nighantu</i>	<i>Guduchyadi varga</i>	<i>Dh. Ni. Guduchyadi varga (Pg. 42)</i>
6.	<i>Sodhala Nighantu</i>	<i>Guduchyadi varga</i>	<i>So. Ni. Guduchyadi varga (Pg. 39,209)</i>

7.	Abhidhanratnamala	Swadu kandh	Abhi. Rat.Swadu kandh (Pg. 3)
8.	Hridayadipaka Nighantu	Dwipaad varga	Hr. Ni. Dwipaad varga (Pg. 25)
9.	Madanpala Nighantu	Abhyadi varga	Ma. Ni. Abhyadi varga (Pg. 140)
10.	Kaiyadev Nighantu	Aushadhi varga	Ka. Ni. Aushadhi varga (Pg. 638)
11.	Raj Nighantu	Moolakadi varga	Ra. Ni. Moolakadi varga (Pg. 167)
12.	Bhavaprakasha Nighantu	Guduchyadi varga	Bh. Ni. Guduchyadi varga (Pg. 373)
13.	Gunaratnamala	Guduchyadi varga	Gu. Rat. Guduchyadi varga (Pg. 258)
14.	Saraswati Nighantu	Latadi varga	Sar. Ni. Latadi varga (Pg. 50)
15.	Laghu Nighantu	Guduchyadi varga	La. Ni. Guduchyadi varga (Pg. 22)
16.	Shaligrama Nighantu	Guduchyadi varga	Sha. Ni. Guduchyadi varga, Vol.7-8 (Pg. 287)
17.	Nighantu Adarsha	Palashadi varga	Ni. Ad. Palashadi varga (Pg. 398)
18.	Priya Nighantu	Pipplyadi varga	Pri. Ni. Pipplyadi varga (Pg. 44)

Sanskrit synonyms of Vidarikand in different Nighantus

S.N	Sanskrit Name	Nighantus																	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
1.	Shukla	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
2.	Swadukanda	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
3.	Shringalika	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-
4.	Vrishyakanda	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-
5.	Vidari	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
6.	Vrishyavalli	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Vidalika	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
8.	Vidarika	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
9.	Vrikshvalli	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Vrikshkanda	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Kandavalli	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	Palashaka	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	Sita	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
14.	Vidaali	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.	Vrishyavallika	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	Bhukushmandi	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	Swadulata	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18.	Gajeshta	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
19.	Vaarivallabha	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20.	Kandaphala	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21.	Koshtri	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-
22.	Ikshugandha	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
23.	Ksheervalli	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
24.	Ksheershukla	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
25.	Payaswini	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
26.	Vallipalash	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
27.	Vallikanda	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
28.	Gajapriya	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
29.	Vajipriya	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
30.	Ikshuvidari	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
31.	Kushmandaki	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32.	Palashika	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
33.	Gajvajipriya	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34.	Vallipalashika	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35.	Kandapalash	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
36.	Kshreshthkakandak	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
37.	Vrishyaparni	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
38.	Mragoli	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
39.	Krishnavallika	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
40.	Bhumikushmanda	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
41.	Swadukandika	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
42.	Vajishita	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-

43.	<i>Vrishyakandika</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
44.	<i>Ikshukandika</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
45.	<i>Shuklakanda</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
46.	<i>Kaamda</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
47.	<i>Vrishya</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
48.	<i>Ikshuvidarika</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
49.	<i>Charukanda</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+

1. *Dhanvantari Nighantu* 2. *Madanpala Nighantu* 3. *Raj Nighantu* 4. *Bhavprakash Nighantu* 5. *Sodhala Nighantu* 6. *Kaiyadev Nighantu* 7. *Shaligram Nighantu* 8. *Priya Nighantu* 9. *Saushrut Nighantu* 10. *Ashtang Nighantu* 11.

Paryayaratnamala 12. *Madanadi Nighantu* 13. *Abhidhanratnamala* 14. *Hridayadipaka Nighantu* 15. *Gunaratnamala* 16. *Saraswati Nighantu* 17. *Laghu Nighantu* 18. *Nighantu Adarsha*.

Properties and action of Vidarikand according to Nighantus

S.N	Nighantu	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Dosha Karma	Other Karma
1.	<i>Dhanvantari Nighantu</i> ^[31]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Vaat-Pitta shamak</i>	<i>Balvardhak, Shukra janan</i>
2.	<i>Raj Nighantu</i> ^[32]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Kapha karak</i>	<i>Rakta-Pitta nashak, Pushti karak, Balya, Veerya vardhak</i>
3.	<i>Bhavprakash Nighantu</i> ^[33]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Snigdha, Guru</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Pitta-Vata nashak</i>	<i>Brimhan, Stanya vardhak, Shukra vardhak, Swarya, Mutral, Jeevani, Balvarnada, Rasayana, Rakta-daha nashak</i>
4.	<i>Kaiyadev Nighantu</i> ^[34]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Snighha, Guru</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Pitta-vata-rakta vicar nashak</i>	<i>Brimhan, Shukrajanan, Mutral, Swarya, Stanya-bala-varna prada, Jeevaniya, Rasayani</i>
5.	<i>Madanpal Nighantu</i> ^[35]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Snigdha, Guru</i>	-	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Pitta-rakta-vata nashak</i>	<i>Brimhani, Stanya-shukrada, Rasayani</i>
6.	<i>Sodhala Nighantu</i> ^[36]	<i>Madhur</i>	-	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Vaat har</i>	<i>Balya, Brimhan, Vrshya, Swarya, Atimutral</i>
7.	<i>Priya Nighantu</i> ^[37]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Vaat-Pitta shamak</i>	<i>Vrishya, Rasayana, Brimhan, Balya, Stanya vardhan, Mutral, Daha -jwar -kshaya nashak</i>
8.	<i>Shaligram Nighantu</i> ^[38]	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Guru</i>	<i>Sheet</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Pitta hara, Kapha vardhak</i>	<i>Brimhana, Balya, Rasayana, Vrshya, Stanyajanana, Shukrala, Dahashamak</i>

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The literary review of various *Ayurvedic* treatises such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Ashtanga Sangraha*, *Kashyapa Samhita*, *Harita Samhita*, *Sharangadhara Samhita*, *Bhela Samhita*, *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Yogratnakara*, and *Bhaishajyaratnavali* reveals that *Vidarikand* has been widely acknowledged for its therapeutic value and potential efficacy. *Charaka Samhita*, classified *Vidarikand* under *Madhura Skandha* and *Snehaopaga Mahakashaya*, with specific applications in conditions like *Rajyakshma*, *Kasa*, *Swasa*, and *Mutrakriccha*. *Sushruta Samhita* highlights it in *Vidarigandhadi gana* and *Pitta Shamana varga*, emphasizing its cooling, rejuvenative, and aphrodisiac properties. Similarly, *Ashtanga Hridaya* and *Ashtanga Sangraha* focused *Vidarikand* in respiratory, urinary, and reproductive disorders, along with *Rasayana karma*. *Bhavaprakasha*, *Yogratnakara*, and *Bhaishajyaratnavali*, described its extensive indication and uses in formulations for *Jwara*, *Prameha*, *Striroga*, *Balroga*, and general debility. The presence of numerous synonyms such as *Vidari*, *Ikshugandha*, *Bhumikushmanda*, and *Payasya* across lexicons like *Amar Kosha* and

Shabdakalpadruma further attests to its widespread recognition and enduring medicinal value existed in ancient times. In present advanced cutting edge era, physicians and researchers should involve and validate the above indications through chemistry lab and pharmacological study about *Vidarikand*.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of classical literatures, it was observed that *Vidarikand (Pueraria tuberosa DC.)* is a versatile medicinal plant with multifaceted pharmacological actions and uses. The *samhitas*, *nighantus*, and other compendia underscores its significance as a role of *Rasayana*, aphrodisiac, galactagogue, and nutritive agent highlighting the broad spectrum of therapeutic applications of *Vidarikand* in respiratory disorders, urinary ailments, reproductive and metabolic disorders. In present scenario, *Vidarikand* may play a pivotal role in promoting overall health and vitality. The consistent documentation of *Vidarikand* across centuries demonstrates its relevance in both preventive and curative healthcare practices of *Ayurveda*.

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